

TRAJECTORY PLANNING IN ROBOTIZED FILAMENT WINDING BY OFFSETTING DIE BOUNDARY TO CONTROL ROVING TENSION

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SUMMARY: Robotized filament winding technology involves a robot that winds a roving impregnated by resin on a die along the directions of stresses the work-piece is submitted in exercise. The robot moves a deposition head along a winding trajectory in order to deposit roving. Trajectory planning is a critical aspect of robotized filament winding technology, since it is responsible for both the tension constancy and the winding time.

The present work shows an original method to determine a winding trajectory that assures the winding tension keeps near to the nominal value. The trajectory is determined as offset of the boundary curve of the winding die along a direction perpendicular to roving stratification orientation. This trajectory allows to satisfy the constraints on geometrical parameters of winding trajectory (i.e. safety distance and winding angle) in order to keep the value of tension near to the nominal one during winding. This means to assure an acceptable quality of the manufactured composite parts.

KEYWORDS: robotized filament winding, composite parts, full section parts, winding tension, mechanical performances, winding trajectory.

INTRODUCTION

Robotized filament winding technology involves a robot that winds a roving impregnated by resin on a die along the directions of stresses the work-piece is submitted in exercise [1-4]. The robot moves a deposition head along a winding trajectory in order to deposit roving. Trajectory planning is a critical aspect of robotized filament winding technology [5-8], since it is responsible for both the tension constancy and the accuracy in roving location on the winding die; therefore, it influences the mechanical properties of the manufactured composite parts. It should take into account winding tension loosen and roving location inaccuracy due to winding speed.

The winding tension, that is applied to roving and has to be as constant as possible during winding, influences directly the compactness and the alignment of the fibres. The composite resistance against loads applied along the roving deposition direction of the resulting part is due both to its fibres and to the presence of defects in the work-piece. Higher is the fibre percentage in a unitary volume, greater is the work-piece mechanical resistance. Therefore, it is possible to adjust the amount of fibres for a unitary volume by means of roving tension that influences fibre compactness. The choice of the value of the winding tension and the need to keep constant the winding tension to the chosen value are two aspects strongly connected to the geometry of the part to wind. If the applied tension is not enough, fibre may present wrinkling or folds along the deposition direction, causing defects in the final composite part

(i.e. “marcels”). At the same time a very high tension value may cause both a fibre damaging and a strong inhomogeneous compactness of the roving along the underlying surface. Solving this trade-off means to determine the value of the tension that allows to minimize the empty spaces, the wrinkling and the folds, and to have a component with a good structural uniformity. In literature some studies exist on the influence of winding tension on composite part quality, even if they are referred to symmetric part shapes that may be obtained by traditional filament winding [9-13].

The present work discusses original criteria for the determination of a winding trajectory assures the roving tension keeps near to the nominal value. The trajectory is calculated as offset of the boundary curve of the winding die along a direction perpendicular to roving stratification orientation. In this way it is possible to satisfy the constraints on geometrical parameters of winding trajectory (about safety distance and winding angle in [14]) in order to keep the value of tension near to the nominal one during winding. The nominal value of roving tension is fixed in such a way to assure good mechanical performances of manufactured composite parts [15-16].

Firstly, the considered asymmetric full section parts are presented. Then, the technological rules that guide the trajectory planning are shown. Finally, the implementation and validation of the planning logics are described to prove the advantage of the proposed planning method as regards winding tension.

FULL SECTION PARTS IN COMPOSITE MATERIAL

A part obtained thanks to the extrusion of a full section along a closed not auto-intersecting path is the family of asymmetric parts that have been considered in the present work. Some examples of asymmetric full section parts are shown in Fig. 1.

The closed path is formed by 3D curves; the part is automatically produced through a sweeping operation. The composite roving used to manufacture the component has an approximate rectangular section smaller than part section. Therefore, the part section filling can be obtained through a continuous location of the roving section. A grid is positioned on the straight section of the part: it has cells with dimensions equal to the roving ones in the straight section, positioned over it (see Fig. 2). The cells represent the various coils of the roving, necessary to define the layers of the whole part section.

Fig. 1: Examples of full section parts

A continuous deposition is implemented starting from one place (such as 1 in Fig. 2) and ending, after a while winding round, in a new one (such as 2) from which a new winding coil starts. The die gives the supporting walls for the most external of the reinforcement, and because of the shape of the section, it is possible to take two or three retaining surfaces into

consideration. It is possible to define two main directions: the first one Y determines the growth of each single layer by approaching single coils, while the second main direction X, which is perpendicular to the first one, constitutes the direction where the multiplication of the layers takes place.

The winding trajectory of the deposition head is a set of points ordered in space; it represents the image of the points of every coil [14-15]. To guarantee an accurate winding of the roving on the die, the winding trajectory must be tangent to the roving trajectory along each contact point between the winding roving and the already wound roving. During the winding must be respected two conditions: i) the roving tension must be as constant as possible; ii) the deposition head and the robot arms should be moved on collision free trajectories, the free roving must not interfere with the die and the whole environment. A control volume, characterized by a safety distance, is generated to value the impacts in order to keep the path outside the considered volume.

Fig. 2: a) Fork and its winding die; b) part cross section.

PLANNING OF THE WINDING TRAJECTORY BY OFFSETTING DIE BOUNDARY

The original method to plan the winding trajectory of a full section part offsets the boundary curve of the winding die. The boundary curve of the winding die corresponds to the shape of the closed path along which a full section is extruded to obtain the part model to manufacture. The boundary curve has the shape of one of the wound coils, as shown in Fig. 3. An example of winding trajectory obtained by offsetting the closed path used to build the fork model is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: a) Winding die of the fork component with one of its winding trajectories;
b) simulation of a planning winding trajectory

The planned trajectory satisfies the two constraints described in the previous paragraph, i.e. the constancy of the winding tension and the control of the safety distance. The safety distance is the minimum distance from the die the deposition system should keep during its movement around the die, in order to avoid collisions with the die during winding. This kind

of winding trajectory avoids decrease in roving tension during winding, i.e. roving loosens, since it is characterized by a trajectory angle (θ) higher than 90° [14, 15]. The trajectory angle is the angle the vector of the deposition system movement, which is tangent to the winding trajectory, forms with the roving direction. Fig. 4-7 show a part of the offsetting trajectory of Fig. 3. The deposition system moves from A_1 to A_4 in Fig. 4 along the trajectory during winding. The trajectory angle is higher than 90° in each of the 4 considered points of the winding trajectory in Fig. 4. The value of the trajectory angle characterizing the offsetting trajectory decreases with the increase of the distance of the winding trajectory from the winding die, as shown in Fig. 5a. The trajectory angle assumes a value of 90° when the winding trajectory is put at infinite distance from the die. The value of the trajectory angle keeps constant along the winding trajectory, as shown in Fig. 5b. This involves a more continuous movement of the deposition system without sudden change in head's direction; thus, favouring to keep constant the tension on the roving. The winding trajectory planned by offsetting the die boundary is characterized by a constant value of the safety distance (d) along the whole trajectory, as shown in Fig. 5b. The value of the safety distance does not depend by the trajectory angle for the trajectory planned by offsetting the die boundary. In fact, if we impose 90° as value of the trajectory angle, we may design the winding trajectory by means of A'_1 , A''_2 , A'''_3 and A''''_4 points in Fig. 6a, but those points do not belong to an offsetting trajectory. The trajectory connecting A'_1 , A''_2 , A'''_3 and A''''_4 points moves near to the winding die and the safety distance decreases from d_1 to d_4 as shown in Fig. 6b. An increase of the safety distance may avoid collisions between the deposition system or the robot arm and the winding die during winding, especially for small parts. Finally, the offsetting technique assures to keep in tension the roving during winding. We consider 2 points on the winding die, A_1 and A_2 , and the corresponding 2 points on the winding trajectory, A'_1 and A'_2 in Fig. 7. The 2 triangles $A_1A'_1O$ and $A_2A'_2O$ are equal, since they have equal two sides and an angle. Therefore, $A_1A'_1 = A_2A'_2$ and $A_1A_2 + A_2A'_2 > A_1A'_1$ that involve an increasing tension value on roving, when the deposition head moves from point A'_1 to point A'_2 along winding. If $A_1A_2 + A_2A'_2 < A_1A'_1$, the length of the unwound roving, leaning out the winding die, increases when the deposition head moves from point A'_1 to A'_2 ; thus, involving the occurrence of tension loosen during winding.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The offsetting approach has been used to plan a set of winding trajectories that have been implemented by means of a robotized cell constituted by an anthropomorphic robot, a unique and innovative device and a winding die, as shown in Fig. 8.a [17]. The robot is an anthropomorphic Kuka, with 6 d.o.f., payload 45 kg, max. reach 2041 mm, work envelope volume 24 m³, repeatability $< \pm 0.15$ mm. The winding device has been designed and built on the basis of compactness, structural lightness, stiffness and functionality principles, in order to guarantee both the maximum dexterity of the robot, to minimize the probability of crashes between the winding die and the components of the cell, and to improve the control of the process parameters for accuracy and repeatability [17-19]. The feeding device shows a modular structure constituted by four critical subgroups or modules Fig. 8b: the main frame, the roving-guide system, the winding tensioner and the deposition system.

Fig. 4: Trajectory angle characterizing an offsetting trajectory

Fig. 5: a) Trajectory angle for different value of the distance of the trajectory from the die; b) Trajectory angle along the whole trajectory.

Fig. 6: a) Safety distance characterizing an offsetting trajectory; b) Safety distance by keeping equal to 90° the trajectory angle

Fig. 7: To tension roving during winding

Fig. 8: a) New robotized filament winding cell; b) feed and deposition system.

The cell has been equipped with a dynamometer Fig. 9a-b, that has been mounted under the winding die, in order to measure the winding tension. A Kistler piezoelectric platform dynamometer (Type 9257 BA) has been used to measure components of the force along three orthogonal directions (F_x , F_y and F_z). The data of tension are determined by a software that has been developed in Labview[®] by National Instrument.

A simple part has been used as benchmark. It is commonly used by an important Italian aeronautic company to test alternative composites manufacturing technologies and systems (see Fig. 9c). The material used for the experimental tests is carbon roving impregnated by epoxy resin, conformed to MIL-R-9300 requirements. The slip roving consists of 12 thousand (12K) filament-count tows. Polyacrilonite (PAN) precursor graphite fibres are used. The slip roving has a 3.2 ± 0.8 mm width and a 0.76 ± 0.85 g/m yield. The part usually requires about 90 revolutions around the supporting die. A set of experimental tests has been designed by means of a factorial experimental plan. Three values of both the safety distance d (40mm-90mm-140mm), shown in Fig. 10, and the nominal speed of the deposition system S (50%-75%-100% of maximum value of the robot linear speed equal to 2 m/s) have been considered. Three replicates of each trajectory have been carried out and, therefore, 27 trajectories of the deposition head have been planned in all. Tension has been set to a value of 70N that assures good performances of manufactured composite parts [17-19].

In Fig. 11 is shown the feed and deposition system moves along a winding trajectory ($d=40$ mm) in order to deposit the roving on the winding die to manufacture the benchmark.

Fig. 9: a) Equipment used to measure winding tension; b) Details of force measurement equipment: A, C= support; B=dynamometer; D=winding die of the irregular ring (dimensions in mm); c) irregular ring.

Fig. 10: Winding trajectories characterized by 3 different value of safety distance.

Fig. 11: Example of winding process - winding trajectory with a safety distance equal to 40mm.

Each benchmark has involved only 6 layers of the whole irregular ring, since the winding trajectory is the same for each layer wound if the process parameters are the same. Each layer is formed by 3 coils (see Fig. 12). The 27 trajectories have been implemented and the winding tension has been measured by the dynamometer for each trajectory.

Fig. 12: Irregular ring section.

The measured winding tension has been put into relationship with the process parameters, the safety distance and the nominal speed of the deposition system, by means of the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The average value of winding tension on roving depends by both the two process parameters. It increases by decreasing the safety distance, but especially by increasing the nominal speed, as shown in Figure 13.

The clutch applies to the roving a tension value of 70 N in static friction conditions before unwinding (nominal value of tension). When the roving is unwound by the spool, the dynamic friction between roving and spool implies a reduction of 5-8% of the tension applied to the roving as regard the static friction conditions. The average value of the winding tension on roving measured by the dynamometer, of about 68.25 N, is higher than that one expected in dynamic conditions. This is probably due to the centrifugal component of the inertial force acting on roving when it moves along a curvilinear regular trajectory. This force component depends directly by the angular speed used to run along the circular path that is proportional to the tangential speed and, therefore, to the winding nominal speed S that has been set to plan the trajectory. This force component has a direction perpendicular to the trajectory and it is oriented outside the trajectory itself. Therefore, this centrifugal force stretches the roving by acting together with the applied tension. The resulting value of tension on roving is nearer, that that due to alternative methods of trajectory planning [16], to the nominal value of tension. The nominal value of tension, 70 N in this case, is that value of tension that assure to manufacture work-pieces characterized by good mechanical performances.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work has shown a simple rule of thumb to plan the trajectory of the deposition system: it is enough to offset the boundary curve of the winding die. The proposed rule may be easily applied to parts obtained by extruding a section along a planar path, such as the benchmark used in this work. This simple rule allows to obtain a winding trajectory that is characterised by a sequence of linear or circular segments along which the deposition head moves in order to deposit the composite roving on the mandrel. This sequence makes the movement of the deposition head more continuous and more harmonious during winding, since it avoids the sudden change in head's direction. In the same time, the winding trajectory planned by offsetting the die boundary has a value of the trajectory angle higher than 90° and constant along the whole trajectory; thus, avoiding decrease in the tension value of the roving

during winding, i.e. roving loosens. The offsetting trajectory is characterized by a safety distance constant along the whole trajectory. By decreasing the value of safety distance or by increasing the nominal speed of the deposition system is possible to increase the winding tension on roving. The offsetting trajectory allows to keep the roving tension very near to the value that assures to manufacture parts characterised by good mechanical performances.

Fig. 13: Main Effect plots of average winding tension vs. process parameters

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